

Petrogale rothschildi X

Essay

Map

Network

In “honour of the Hon. Walter Rothschild”: local collecting for international connections

The 1903 edition of the *Novitates Zoologicae* contained a short note by Oldfield Thomas, the renowned curator of Mammals at the British Museum of Natural History, naming a new species of rock wallaby from Western Australia (fig 1). For this new species he proposed the name, *Petrogale rothschildi*, in acknowledgment of the financial support provided by the second Baron Rothschild to the collecting work by John Tunney, the Western Australian Museum’s collector. The identification of the new species was based on a skin collected by Tunney in July 1901.

While the naming of a new species was an important contribution to the list of Western Australia’s fauna it was also important in connecting the ambitions of a small group of individuals. The collaboration worked across large distances with this small group combining local knowledge, colonial aspiration and ambitions of empire to position a piece of Western Australia in a network of collecting that stretched from Western Australia to the United Kingdom and beyond.

Tunney started as Museum Collector in 1895 and for the next five years his efforts were funded by the Museum, overseen by the Museum Committee and guided by the then Director, Bernard Woodward. In trips to the Murchison, Pilbara, Kimberley, and South-west regions of Western Australia, Tunney contributed an extensive range of natural history specimens, as well as ethnographic materials, to the Western Australian Museum. The parcels that were regularly despatched contained a mix of birds, mammals, insects, the occasional fish, along with photographs and various Aboriginal artefacts and Ancestral Remains.

In 1900, Woodward responded to a request from banker turned zoologist, Lionel Walter Rothschild, for an exchange between the Western Australian Museum and Rothschild’s personal museum at Tring Park. The Western Australian Museum was asked to send Western Australian birds (“as itemised in the list provided”) in return for a selection of birds from the United Kingdom.

By this time, Tunney's collecting efforts had significantly expanded the Western Australian Museum collection, and its broadly representative collections of Western Australian fauna were increasingly utilised by Woodward in responding to requests for exchange. In return for the birds, mammals, insects and ethnographic items despatched, the Museum received specimens of animals and cultural items from other parts of the world. Other areas targeted included arts and crafts from ancient and contemporary Europe, along with antiquities and ethnographic materials from other parts of the world. This exchange programme was a central element in Woodward's plans to establish for the people of Western Australia a place where they could experience WA and the world. Tunney's collections were central to this plan, though other paid and casual collectors and donors also contributed.

Rothschild, too, relied on an extensive network of collectors to fulfil his plans. Where Woodward largely concentrated on Western Australia, Rothschild 'collected the world'. He established a global network of collectors to drive plans for his vision of a global natural history museum. The total number of collectors contributing to the Museum at Tring Park is unknown but is estimated to be in excess of 400. Once he started collecting for Rothschild, Tunney became a small cog in a much bigger machine.

The success of the initial exchange soon led to a more commercial arrangement that resulted in Rothschild underwriting Tunney's collecting, with Tring Park receiving the first choice of specimens. However, with this arrangement came new instructions that included a request for Tunney to travel to the Northern Territory to work through country around the Alligator River system. Planning for this work began almost immediately, broadening the range of specimens that Tunney would ultimately collect but shifting the emphasis of his collecting. It is not clear whether the acquisition of Northern Territory animals and ethnographic items fitted the long-term plans for a museum of Western Australia, but the opportunity to service the needs of the biggest collector of natural history specimens of the time was too good to pass.

Rothschild's arrangement with Woodward to finance Tunney's collecting was confirmed by early 1901, as Tunney was working through the Pilbara, which included trips to the offshore islands. One of these trips to the islands off Cossack in July 1901 was largely unsuccessful with Tunney writing that it was due to incorrect local advice that Lewis Island was the best to place to collect. However, Tunney went on to record that on Enderby Island he managed to acquire seven rock wallabies, one of which became the holotype for *Petrogale rothschildi*. In his published note, Thomas recorded Cossack as the collecting location, though based on Tunney's correspondence it is more likely to have been collected on Enderby Island, just off the Pilbara coast to the west of the Burrup Peninsula. The source of confusion may have resulted from the Western Australian Museum specimen label tied to the skin, which recorded Cossack as the location.

Although the Enderby Island/Cossack specimen was collected during the period of Rothschild's funding it was sent to Oldfield Thomas at the British Museum of Natural History rather than to Rothschild's museum at Tring Park. Thomas, who had started with the Natural History Museum in a clerical post in 1876, was transferred to work under the Keeper of Zoology, Dr Albert Gunther. In turn, Gunther had mentored the teenage Walter Rothschild and assisted in the plans for Rothschild's museum. A strong friendship developed between Gunther and Rothschild, which may have also contributed to Thomas' thought process when recognising Rothschild and his financial support of Tunney's collecting practice.

Ultimately, the rock wallaby would be one of 18 mammal species dedicated to Rothschild, along with more than two hundred other animals (mainly birds) that were also named after the man.

Rothschild's contribution to natural history and natural science collections was significant and his passion and enthusiasm for his collecting enterprise had a major impact on our understanding of zoology and the natural world and on museum collections around the globe.

From a small island off the Pilbara coast the efforts of one individual were connected to the global interests of another via a network of intermediaries working collaboratively to advance our knowledge of science and the natural history of Western Australia.

Figures:

1. Holotype of *Petrogale rothschildi*, collected by J.T. Tunney in 1901. Courtesy Natural History Museum, CC0-1.0.
2. *Petrogale rothschildi*, Rothschild's rock wallaby, Courtesy Jiri Lochman, RAD-200.

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